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The ERMES chatbot: A conversational communication tool for improved emergency management and disaster risk reduction

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ABSTRACT

The increased occurrence and severity of worldwide disasters, exacerbated by the impact of climate change, pose significant challenges to emergency management, calling for novel and more effective Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) approaches. Despite the phenomenological differences of diverse hazards and the heterogeneity of local policies and governance structures, effective communication systems are needed to better manage the available resources in all phases of the emergency management cycle, especially in the case of cross-border events. In this work, we present the design, implementation, and validation of a novel tool for emergency management, i.e., the ERMES Chatbot: a mobile-based conversational communication system developed to facilitate real-time bidirectional communication between control centres, in-field forces, and citizens. The methodology used to create the ERMES Chatbot is grounded on the user-centred design approach, which entails end-user involvement in all key phases of the development, including the definition of the end-user requirements, the technical design, and the final validation of the proposed solution. The co-design approach involved several organisations belonging to the DRR domain, which includes a gamified experience for citizens and is iteratively validated through four in-field demonstration events based on realistic emergency scenarios with the involvement of emergency practitioners, volunteering organisations, and citizens.

1. Introduction

Globally, communities are facing an alarming increase in hazards. The frequency and intensity of events such as floods, wildfires, and storms have significantly heightened, presenting a substantial risk to various regions worldwide. These escalating events are widely believed to be strongly linked to climate change, which exacerbates environmental vulnerabilities and amplifies the potential for catastrophic events [1].

The field of Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) is encountering growing complexities in its initiatives to alleviate and react to these intensifying risks, also due to the following challenges.

- The diverse range of hazards poses distinct challenges that necessitate tailored and adaptive approaches to risk reduction. When dealing with rapidly rising floodwaters, raging wildfires, or unpredictable storm patterns, different strategies may be required in the different phases of the emergency management cycle.
- The availability and diversity of data sources further complicate the intricate landscape of DRR. Accurate and up-to-date information is indispensable for accurate risk assessment, early warning systems, response planning and execution, and post-

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event recovery. Nevertheless, collecting, integrating, and analysing data from various sources pose substantial technical and logistical challenges.

- The geographical and administrative heterogeneity across regions introduces additional complexity to DRR efforts. Different areas showcase distinct socio-economic and cultural traits and diverse governance structures and policies that may negatively affect the effectiveness of DRR measures. Adapting approaches to address local contexts while simultaneously considering cross-regional collaboration and coordination has emerged as an essential factor for the success of risk reduction and resilience-building endeavours [2].

Despite the phenomenological differences of diverse hazards and the heterogeneity of local policies and governance structures, effective communication systems are always beneficial to better manage the available resources in all phases of the emergency management cycle, especially in the case of cross-border events. Differentiating the communication to reach as many citizens as possible is a pillar of modern DRR strategies, which are based on a community-centred perspective that leverages local knowledge and engages several actors as resources to identify, monitor, assess and potentially collaborate to respond to disasters [3]. Communication tools that enable simple and personalised interactions amplify the effectiveness of prevention, response, and monitoring practices. These tools can contribute to existing processes if they are well-aligned and integrated with operational procedures. They can also significantly improve the inclusion of citizens in the process, assigning them an active role.

This work presents a novel conversational system that enables rapid and effective bidirectional communication among citizens, field forces, and control centres.

The contributions of this work are.

- The design of a novel mobile communication tool, including a set of simple yet effective functionalities that can be useful for different hazards. The tool enables multiple stakeholders, such as decision-makers, operation managers and technicians of control centres, in-field personnel, and citizens, to use a common platform to exchange relevant information throughout the entire emergency management cycle. The design includes a gamification strategy for improving citizens' awareness and engagement.
- The implementation of such a communication tool, which leverages a gamified conversational approach and a chat-based interface implemented using state-of-the-art web-based technologies and Application Program Interfaces to enable easy integration of the proposed tool with existing DRR solutions.
- Validating the proposed tool is performed via four in-field demonstration events based on realistic emergency scenarios, with the involvement of emergency practitioners, volunteering organisations, and citizens.

The novelty of this work lies in the proposed tool itself, which borrows some ideas from previous works related to mobile applications and chatbots for DRR. We design, develop, and validate this user-friendly conversational interaction following the user-centred approach, considering realistic scenarios defined from high-impact historic emergency events and involving several emergency practitioners, volunteering organisations, and citizens. We name our solution *ERMES Chatbot*, where *ERMES* is an acronym derived from "Enhancing Resiliency to Manage Emergency Situations" and alludes to the ancient Greek deity *Hermes*, who was the messenger of the gods. The *ERMES Chatbot* can be effectively used by different stakeholders, including emergency management practitioners such as first responders and citizens. This work primarily focuses on the citizen dimension (requirements, functions, experience, and improvements). The detailed description and validation of the functionalities for professionals are left as future work.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we review related works about the interplay between DRR and ICT solutions, focusing on the role of mobile technology and applications. In Section 3, the design methodology and the resulting principles are described. Section 4 describes the *ERMES Chatbot* functionalities, implementation and technical details. Section 5 presents the results and analysis of the user tests conducted with citizens. Finally, Section 6 outlines conclusions from our study and potential future works.

2. Related works

The challenges the decision-makers encounter before, during, and after a disaster have consequences in timely data collection, including information on sheltering needs, infrastructure damages, and nutritional needs assessment [4,5]. Digital solutions applied to the DRR domain have emerged as a powerful enabler, providing innovative tools that enhance preparedness, response, and recovery efforts in the face of disasters. From early warning systems to real-time data analysis and communication platforms, digital solutions are vital in improving decision-making, enhancing stakeholder coordination, and empowering communities to mitigate and respond to disasters effectively [6]. As the complexity of disaster risks continues to evolve, integrating digital solutions into DRR strategies becomes more crucial, offering opportunities to leverage technological advancements and harness the power of data-driven insights for effective disaster management.

About 95 % of the global population is covered by mobile networks, and the percentage of people subscribed to mobile services is expected to be at 70 % in 2025 [7]. The ubiquity of mobile devices, with their user-friendly interfaces and widespread adoption, empowers communities to participate in crowdsourcing efforts actively, amplifying the role of local communities, significantly enhancing real-time information flow and enabling a more comprehensive understanding of evolving disaster scenarios [8]. Different studies and reviews analyse the integration of ad-hoc mobile applications into DRR to understand the main features a mobile application should have and which are the main challenges to address to build reliable systems [9]. These applications leverage two main sensors: the GPS to enable precise geolocation tracking, enhancing situational awareness and facilitating efficient resource allocation in disaster scenarios; and the camera functionalities to capture and share real-time visual data, facilitating rapid damage assessment and pro-

viding valuable information for timely response and recovery operations [10]. The location information helps field forces coordinate effectively and eases decision-making throughout all the emergency management phases. Moreover, most mobile applications leverage Geographic Information Systems (GIS), open data like OpenStreetMap (OSM) [11,12], and Google Maps [13]. Crucial aspects of mobile application adoption are user-friendliness [9], an acceptable purpose, and meaningful content and actions [14]. Intuitive interfaces and seamless user experiences accommodate individuals with varying levels of technological proficiency [15]. Moreover, effective user interaction is crucial to support complex tasks such as crowdsourced data collection, which is the mechanism enabling the users to act "as a sensor" [16–19]. For example, Aydin et al. [20] proposed a mobile application that includes damage estimation, location search for essential facilities, reporting and searching for missing persons, and resource search and reporting. Geldenhuys [21] proposes an application to ask for help by recording and sending audio messages while allowing sharing of photos, locations, and text. Other mobile applications introduced the possibility for citizens to perform new activities, such as receiving timely and adapted multi-channel communication [22,23], learning about environmental hazards, climate change and safe behaviours [24] and collaborating on territory monitoring via crowdsourcing [25,26]. These examples show how ad-hoc mobile applications can help facilitate information exchange among control rooms, in-field agents and citizens.

The advantages of integrating mobile solutions in DRR are evident, including promoting citizens as proactive agents and the timely distribution of personalised warnings and communications that could be addressed to specific population segments and geographic areas. Another advantage of mobile devices is their ability to be wirelessly used and stay functional during disasters. With a power source or access to portable chargers and Internet connectivity, individuals can use their phones to provide crucial information and access disaster management applications.

However, mobile applications often require users to navigate through a Graphical User Interface (GUI). This navigation scheme involves understanding and interacting with various visual elements like buttons, menus, and icons. While mobile applications can offer a rich, interactive experience, they can also be challenging for specific user types and contexts. For instance, individuals unfamiliar with modern technology, those with visual impairments, or even users trying to access services where they cannot focus on a screen may find GUIs less accessible [27]. Moreover, ad-hoc mobile applications often involve complex development processes, ongoing maintenance requirements, and challenges in app distribution within crowded marketplaces.

On the other hand, conversational interfaces, such as chatbots, mimic human conversation, allowing users to interact using natural language, either typed or spoken. This approach may reduce the learning curve, especially for those who are not tech-savvy or are differently abled [28,29]. Chatbots can support communication processes during disasters as an additional bidirectional communication channel, allowing information sharing between authorities and citizens while reducing the risk of Infodemics, i.e., information overload during crisis events. ([30]). Chatbots are particularly fit for educating people, giving advice about the correct behaviours in an emergency, or suggesting possible preventive measures to avoid dangerous situations [31]. Chatbots can be implemented as ad-hoc applications or developed by leveraging platforms like Telegram, Whatsapp or Facebook Messenger.

Furthermore, using existing platforms offers significant advantages in software development, maintenance, distribution, and effortless support with different hardware and operating systems. However, using a specific platform ties the development to that platform, forcing software updates every time the host platform APIs or policies change [32]. Additionally, some users might have privacy concerns and thus hesitate to use third-party systems for security-related applications [33].

Several examples of chatbots applied to DRR are based on existing platforms, and they generally focus on a specific task or in a particular phase of the disaster risk management cycle. For the prevention phase, a possible strategy involves creating tools designed to assist individuals in preparing for potential future disasters, encompassing safe behaviours and providing comprehensive training. Syed et al. [34] proposed this approach by developing a closed-domain question-answering Telegram chatbot to train Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) employees in crisis management. Another approach for the preparedness phase is the development of chatbots for in-field data collection and dissemination. Another example of this approach is the *Monitoring Cuaca* (= weather monitoring) Telegram chatbot [35], which systematically gathers real-time local weather information from the ground and presents it, along with weather forecasts, through a simple and intuitive interface. A similar strategy is implemented by the *System Monitoring* [36] Telegram chatbot: a water monitoring tool connected with sensors measuring water levels and pH in a river. When these metrics exceed predefined thresholds, the chatbot promptly issues alerts to notify relevant stakeholders. This real-time alerting mechanism enhances the proactive nature of the system, enabling timely responses and helping to increase the awareness of potential environmental risks associated with water quality in the monitored river. Usually, prevention and preparedness chatbots aim to provide one-way information, and they do not actively engage users. In the response and recovery phase, chatbots shall focus on facilitating operations like reporting, requesting assistance from people in need, and receiving and sharing helpful information. With this objective, the *Uchaguzi Kenya* chatbot [37] has been developed as a Facebook bot to facilitate reporting in the event of violence and misconduct during the elections in Kenya. It allows users to submit reports specifying the kind of issue and a textual description, with the option to include location and images. Similarly, the *EmergencyReporter* chatbot [38] allows the reporting of damages, situations requiring repair, and restoration of damaged properties, allowing users to send photos and other pertinent information. Ahmady [39] used Telegram to develop a chatbot tailored for foreigners in Japan who may not be familiar with the language. This chatbot is specifically designed to provide crucial information during emergencies, offering details on the nearest evacuation locations, railway stations, and facilitating the exchange of information on nearby disasters. The choice of the English language ensures that non-native speakers can access essential information promptly and effectively, contributing to their safety and well-being during emergencies in Japan. In some cases, DRR chatbots have been linked to a web-based application displaying all information, thus enhancing the decision-making process and activity coordination. The *Rimay* chatbot [40] is an example of this approach because its web application allows a coordinator to create event-specific tasks and assign them to a specific volunteer in the field, who can send reports with attached files to the coordinator using the chatbot interface.

With the rise of Large Language Models such as GPT-3 [41] - the model underlying ChatGPT, chatbots have evolved with the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), enhancing their capabilities in processing user input and providing valuable information. AI-based DRR chatbots include systems like *Clara*¹, the American Red Cross chatbot meant to help American citizens with blood donation procedures and give information on available shelters and support services in the aftermath of a disaster. Another example is the SPECECA bot [42], which leverages AI models to process textual and audio input to help users understand and practise first-aid manoeuvres. Thanks to its connection to other services, it can alert healthcare personnel and post on social media. A similar approach has been used by DisBot ([43]), a chatbot that collects its knowledge from social media to build a dynamic knowledge graph to generate responses to users asking for disaster-related information. These applications leverage AI algorithms to analyse and comprehend user queries, allowing for more nuanced and context-aware responses and emphasising the conversational approach. However, it is crucial to note that while AI plays an important role in processing user input, there should be careful control over its outputs, particularly in the context of critical information sharing during disasters. Implementing controls over AI-generated outputs is paramount to ensure information integrity and reliability, especially in DRR applications.

In this work, we design, implement, and validate a novel DRR tool using a user-centred approach. The tool we call the ERMES Chatbot consists of a textual chatbot that includes a set of functionalities that support the entire management cycle and different hazards, including those impacting cross-boundary conditions. To achieve this goal, we defined the main functionalities considering the previous literature and adopting a co-design approach involving emergency manager practitioners. As a part of a more comprehensive DRR platform, the ERMES Chatbot, based on Telegram, is functionally connected with a web-based dashboard for professionals, supporting the data visualisation of information collected via ERMES Chatbot and other sources, the exchange of communication for missions management and early warning purposes. The ERMES Chatbot is the module that enables bidirectional communication between a control room and users on the territory. In order to address different needs, two sets of differentiated capabilities for professionals and citizens are offered, the latter addressed by a gamification strategy to boost their engagement. The collection of user feedback and realistic in-field demonstrations are the iterative techniques applied to the progressive validation of the solution.

3. Methodology

The literature offers design principles for conversational agents applied to crisis management [44], where user-centred approaches are crucial to design optimal user experiences and interactions suitable for DRR scenarios. The User-Centred Design (UCD) approach was born from the seminal work of Donald Norman, who reinterpreted the human-machine interaction, moving the focus from the system to the users [45]. The main pillars of the UCD approach are (1) the active engagement of end users from the beginning of the process to orient the problem-solving and ideation on real needs. All the actors are considered precious sources of information and knowledge, indispensable for realising acceptable solutions [46]; (2) the multi-disciplinarity as a combination of different skills and perspectives contributing to the definition of effective and efficient solutions; this principle widens the participatory nature of the approach recommending to promote the direct interaction of technical and domain experts with end-users, to promote better technical solutions based on a deep comprehension of the needs and constraints of the beneficiaries; (3) the iterative and evolving prototyping as a space to test and early fail to take better decisions ([47]). Over time, the UCD has been formalised ([48]) and expanded to be widely adopted as a reference in many application fields. The iterative evaluation is a core activity that design-oriented approaches and software development ones (such as Lean, Agile, and Scrum) have in common. As a design solution develops, the knowledge and understanding of the context get deeper, reducing the cognitive distance between the design model (specified and implemented by the designers and incorporated in the software) and the user model (the cognitive representation the users build on the system and how to interact with it). The closer the two models are, the more positive the user experience will be [45]. In this perspective, the user interface assumes crucial importance to enable frictionless interaction and allow the users to reach their scopes.

The UCD is a process consisting of four phases: (1) context of use understanding; (2) user requirements specifications; (3) design solutions sketching and prototyping; (4) iterative evaluations against requirements ([48]). Adopting the user-centred approach for designing and developing conversational UI allows focusing the solution on the specific context and users to maximise the user experience (UX). In addition, direct user engagement anticipates and facilitates introducing and adopting the solution [49].

In this work, we followed the UCD approach, reframed into our context in three phases: 1) the user research, aimed at collecting the user requirements, which we successively translate into technical requirements 2) the design of the solution and its prototyping 3) the iterative validation of the solution, through iterative user feedback collection and four in-field demonstration events, aimed to assess and improve the UX and usability of the ERMES Chatbot. We now detail the key activities conducted in each of the UCD phases.

1. **USER RESEARCH.** Early and continuous collaboration with local stakeholders is essential to carry out data collection activities to gather user requirements throughout the process. Specific user research activities we conducted are 1) an ad-hoc online survey to investigate needs and gaps in current DRR systems and procedures; 2) an International User Requirement Workshop (IURW) to co-design the ERMES Chatbot requirements with international stakeholders in the field of DRR; 3) local workshops, one in each of the four pilot countries, to extend the requirement collection activity considering the local perspective.
2. **DESIGN and PROTOTYPING.** The data, insights, and learnings derived from the user research allow the identification, definition, and concretisation of viable solutions and functions, interactions, and interface features to be developed. In this phase, the high-level user requirements and UX indications were progressively translated into functional requirements and high-fidelity mock-ups, which were discussed with the technical teams to assess the feasibility and with final users to refine

¹ <https://www.redcrossblood.org/>.

them and test the usability and acceptance. Incremental prototyping [50] is a core activity of the UCD that leverages multiple visualisation techniques such as scenarios, diagrams, and sketches that support the discussion of the solutions between the end users and technicians, and allow the exploration of diverse solutions before implementing them, preventing decisional errors through more informed and collaborative decisions. For instance, user flows, navigation and architecture patterns that do not effectively bring the users to reach the given goals offer the chance to envisage alternatives. Such an approach allowed us to efficiently develop the first ERMES Chatbot release.

3. **VALIDATION & USER FEEDBACK.** The combination of different usability evaluation methods, including the cognitive walkthrough, the heuristic evaluation conducted by experts, intermediate user feedback surveys and user tests with citizens, supports the continuous improvement of the overall system usability [51]. A group of three UX experts performed the heuristic evaluation on the first ERMES Chatbot release to identify a first set of usability issues, considering the [52] usability standard, the Nielsen guidelines on the usability of interactive systems [53], and additional guidelines on chatbot design related to the dialogue flow (including initiative, input modality, and feedback messages), and content [54,55]. We asked each expert to provide design recommendations and sketches, which were then used to support the discussions with developers. After implementing the UX experts' recommendations, four pilot cases were conducted across Europe for about 18 months. Every pilot case was led by a different organisation and based in a specific EU region, namely: 1) Corsica (France), coordinated by the Fire and Rescue Service of Haute-Corse; 2) Piedmont (Italy), led by the Regional Civil Protection; 3) Catalonia (SP), coordinated by the Pau Costa Foundation and 4) Thessaloniki (Greece), led by the Hellenic Rescue Team with the support of the Hellenic Ministry of Defence. In each pilot case, one in-field demonstration was organised to test the ERMES Chatbot in a simulated yet realistic setting, and periodic tests were conducted by the pilot leader, who provided feedback on a monthly basis. Each in-field demonstration included a user feedback session as well as specific user tests, the outcome of which is discussed in detail in Section 5. The in-field demonstrations were planned on a storyline defined in collaboration with local responders organisations, including typical activities executed during the three macro-phases of the emergency management cycle: **prevention & preparedness, detection & response, and restoration & adaptation.**
 - 1) In the **Prevention & Preparedness** phase of the simulated wildfire storyline, the focus is on proactive measures to mitigate fire risks. Professionals consult sub-seasonal weather forecasts to inform their prevention strategies, particularly in light of abnormally dry and hot conditions. Using the ERMES Chatbot, different users identified based on their geolocation and/or role (professionals, volunteers, citizens/reporters) can be asked to execute specific activities and reports. Concurrently, the control room can combine the data received from the field with short-term fire risk forecasts. When high-risk levels (orange/red) are forecasted, surveillance is implemented. This involves in-field personnel patrolling high-risk areas and updating their status and position via the ERMES Chatbot. In parallel, operation managers at control centres or environmental agencies can disseminate early warnings, including preventive messages to the local population (citizens) using the web-based dashboard. The early warning messages are received by citizens via the ERMES Chatbot as a message.
 - 2) During the **Detection & Response**, citizens can report the presence of smoke and flames via the ERMES Chatbot as well as via social media platforms (e.g., Twitter/X). According to the data received, patrol units can be swiftly dispatched to the estimated fire location to confirm the event. Their findings and visual evidence are communicated back to the control centre through a report created using the ERMES Chatbot. This information, along with social media reports, is centralised and displayed on the ERMES web dashboard, facilitating an informed and coordinated response. Throughout the fire suppression phase, while reports are received from citizens, team leaders can keep updated on the status of their missions, their location and operational activity through the ERMES Chatbot, hopefully culminating in the successful dousing of the fire.
 - 3) The **Restoration & Adaptation** phase is characterised by a shift towards recovery and learning. After a fire is extinguished, efforts are directed towards assessing the damages and understanding the impact of the fire in the affected area. This involves conducting detailed mapping of the burned regions to evaluate the extent of the damage. Besides the satellite data, in-field reports about vegetation conditions crowdsourced via the ERMES Chatbot complement the empirical base, incorporating all collected data that practitioners comprehensively analyse (e.g., evaluate the vegetation's recovery after the fire) to plan actions for minimising potential future fires in neighbouring areas.

Citizens can always read tips and take quizzes to improve and test their knowledge of hazards and self-protection behaviours.

During each demonstration, the ERMES Chatbot was tested by professional users and citizens. In particular, a sample of citizens was involved in user tests to carefully assess the ERMES Chatbot functionalities in detail [56]. All the activities provided empirical shreds of evidence elaborated in design recommendations and discussed reorienting strategic decisions, fixing errors, and refining user interactions.

4. Implementation of the ERMES chatbot for citizens

In this section, we describe in detail the implementation of the methodology outlined in Section 3 and summarised in Table 1. We conduct all activities in collaboration with emergency management practitioners in four European countries, France, Greece, Italy and Spain, where local stakeholders have been engaged and actively involved in all described phases. Overall, we engaged a large network of DRR stakeholders was engaged, including 21 organisations of Practitioners (e.g., Civil Protection, Firefighters, Forest Services, Medical Services, and Volunteers Associations), 11 Public administrations (e.g., Local Authorities, Environmental Agencies, Security bodies, Urban Planners, Policymakers), 10 Research bodies, 3 Private companies. In total, 52 organisations, about 240 people,

Table 1
– Methodology implementation.

	Online survey	International User Requirements Workshop (IURW)	Local workshops	End-user feedback sessions after in-field demonstrations
Description	List of closed-ended questions, each with a pre-defined list of answer options.	A 2-day workshop involving interactive activities with a large sample of practitioners and end-users.	Meetings are set with local end-users (i.e., wildfire management authorities from their regions/countries) based on the IURW structure.	In-field tests and demonstrations to validate and improve the ERMES solutions to end users.
Format	Online	Virtual (due to the pandemic)	In-person/Virtual	In-person/Hybrid/Virtual
Key dates	Released on the December 21, 2020	Double event on the 24th and February 25, 2021	Each partner sets them up individually from March 2021 onwards	In-field demonstrations in 4 countries: October 2022; February 2023; October 2023; December 2023
Attendees	49 valid replies from 29 organisations across 16 countries	90 participants from 65 organisations across 18 countries	48 participants from the four pilot cases (France, Italy, Spain and Greece)	53 organisations, 121 practitioners and 159 citizens in four countries (France, Italy, Spain and Greece)
Outputs	Current informative needs and gaps in DRR procedures/tools	Early user requirement collection and focus on data exchange needs within the territory	Localisation of requirements and functionalities definition	Iterative feedback and validation of the implemented functionalities and interactive strategies

out of which 37 citizens, took an active role in the overall process. In the following, we describe the process we adopted to design and develop the ERMES Chatbot, which benefits from previous experiences [26,57].

4.1. ERMES chatbot requirements: collection and definition

The ERMES Chatbot design and development was grounded on the UCD approach involving many stakeholders, including DRR practitioners, decision-makers, and citizens. The engaged stakeholder group included several organisations belonging to the four pilot countries. An initial online survey by 49 respondents from 29 organisations in 16 different countries allowed us to identify the current needs and gaps in DRR. Nearly 90 % of respondents considered the integration of the ERMES Chatbot into the communication channels “very important” or “important” to improve communication with citizens and volunteers during fire-hazardous situations. Similarly, the capability to receive reports from citizens was generally considered very important (more than 60 %) or moderately important (29.2 %). The most used chat tool for communication in emergency management was WhatsApp (80 %), followed by Telegram (40 %). Information provided by trained citizens, such as volunteers, was considered reliable. Also, the majority of the responders expressed an explicit interest in receiving pictures (61 %) and videos (55 %) from the field, highlighting a clear preference for multimedia and geolocated content (75 % and 65 %, respectively). Text messages are considered also helpful (63 %), whereas audio (voice reports) are deemed as less relevant (25 %).

The outputs of the initial survey were used to design the International User Requirements Workshop (IURW), which 90 people from 18 countries attended. The IURW aimed to collect end-user requirements via co-design sessions, and it was followed by four local workshops conducted in Italy (Piedmont region), France (Corse), Spain (Catalonia region) and Greece (Thessaloniki municipality). For each workshop, a facilitator experienced with the UCD approach was appointed and trained to moderate co-design sessions in local languages, supported by ad-hoc training and visual materials encouraging the requirements elicitation². While the IURW focused on collecting requirements at the national and European levels, the subsequent local workshops enabled us to better understand the needs of regional and local stakeholders. As a result, 128 user requirements were formulated and categorised per DRR phases (Prevention and preparedness, Detection and response, and Restoration and Adaptation³). Afterwards, they were collaboratively described and prioritised according to the stakeholders' inputs.

Moreover, qualitative and quantitative data collected by the user research activities provided a common understanding of actual DRR activities, in terms of tasks and communication flows and types of actors, furtherly described as personas and then user profiles: **control room operators** (including roles such as operation managers, team managers, and domain specialists); **in-filed agents** (including professional responders and volunteers) and **citizens**. Each user profile refers to different tasks and specific touchpoints.

The idea of developing the ERMES Chatbot was a request expressed by the involved stakeholders, who highlighted the opportunity to leverage existing platforms instead of creating another additional stand-alone ad-hoc mobile application. The reason for this indication is twofold. On the one hand, to simplify system and data management, and to avoid distributing and fragmenting data in different systems. On the other hand, to facilitate the adoption, promoting regular use. The user requirements covering different user profiles and needs, confirm the general concept of the ERMES Chatbot as a mobile solution suitable to support the bidirectional communication of in-field agents and citizens with control room operators. The ERMES Chatbot's primary goal is to enable users on the territory to create and send reports about hazards, events, and environmental information to the control room. The users acting as reporters are provided with a tool that guides them in producing data in the form of structured information and provisions that ensure interoperability between control room systems and users. The need to distinguish the functionalities of the ERMES Chatbot according to the user profile emerged. Although the reporting task can be performed by all in-field users, the analysis of goals, motivation and

² The detailed description of the workshop methodology and outcomes is outside the scope of this paper, and it is left for future work.

³ Phases of the DRR systemic approach supported by the European Commission, based on the CBD guidance on ecosystem-based approaches to climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction and adaptation to climate change <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-14/cop-14-dec-05-en.pdf>.

tasks of citizens and professionals brings us to design two versions of the ERMES Chatbot, with two sets of specific functionalities, one dedicated to citizens and one for professionals. The user role information, stored within their access credentials, ensures that upon logging into the bot, grants access to the appropriate set of functionalities aligned with the specific user role.

The ERMES Chatbot for citizens aims to introduce users to a collaborative concept of DRR and engage them as proactive citizens. The procedure to guide citizens in creating geolocated reports required different design iterations to simplify the user flow as much as possible, exploiting the conversational UI. Considering the user journey of citizens, the ERMES Chatbot functions have been designed as activities to be performed via conversational UI.

1. The **onboarding** is the phase in which the user enters the system for the first time, and it is conceived as a brief conversation, starting with a welcome message explaining the ERMES Chatbot's purpose and the actions enabled. The user can decide how to proceed with the conversation, learning more about using the bot and following a short tutorial or "changing the topic" of the conversation.
2. The core function of the ERMES Chatbot is **reporting**, the activity that allows users to send geolocated information to the control room of the local authority. The report creation has been designed as a procedure divided into microtasks to simplify and guide the users in inputting the data as the control room operators require. With stakeholders' collaboration, requirements were collected, specifying types of data to be collected, organised per hazard/event, and which parameters and formats are considered acceptable and useful for the professionals. This procedure has been the object of different design iterations aimed at identifying the balance between the professionals' need for the accuracy of crowdsourced data and the citizens' need for a quicker and simpler procedure.
3. Training the users to become reporters is a strategic section of the system, enabling the users to learn how to properly use and exchange information via the ERMES Chatbot. Conceived as a **micro-learning** activity, dedicated content engages the users in Tips and Quizzes on hazards, safe behaviours, and environmental observation. That way, users can access small, focused, bite-sized pieces of information (micro-content) and challenge themselves to test their skills.
4. To receive and consult geolocated **communications** created by the control room operators and spread to users according to their location and/or preferred location is the function that enhances and supports emergency communication, including early warnings and updates from the local authorities.
5. Peer review is a very relevant function enabled by the ERMES Chatbot. By reviewing other citizens' reports and receiving reviews on their reports, every user can contribute to data maintenance. This function helps to build collaboration among citizens and between citizens and control room operators.
6. Finally, **personalisation** of the ERMES Chatbot settings, is here considered as an activity in which the user knows and shapes the system functioning and interaction according to their preferences (language, spatial and temporal filters, username and time zone customisation).

The visual prototyping allowed us to ideate, compare and refine different UX/UI solutions for the defined user activities. The incremental prototyping specified: the flow of the different tasks, the conversation structure and affordances (questions, feedback, pre-defined prompts or commands) according to a few guiding principles identified and agreed upon with stakeholders and developers.

- **Simple user interaction** based on an intuitive conversational mechanism, driving the person to enjoy and use all the provided features properly.
- **Friendly and context-wise conversational interaction**, aimed at reducing as much as possible the cognitive load required for processing texts, defined as the total amount of mental effort. It is influenced by the manner in which content is presented [58], and it is affected by the information overload (quantity) and the usability of instructions, information, copy and micro-copy, commands, feedback, and UI elements [59,60]. In addition, in the DRR context, the UX is especially affected by the ongoing situation and the person's condition and emotions. It is known that we are less efficient in processing text than images, and our capability decreases more when we are in a critical emotional state [61].
- Capability to express **empathy and trustworthiness** through linguistic capabilities by implementing a simple and straightforward conversation [62].

Following and applying a user-centred design approach instead of a technology-driven process broadens our range of action: design activities did not define only the technical system and the user interaction. The early definition of the user journey allowed us to complete the design of the entire life cycle of the data collected through the ERMES Chatbot, defining recommendations and solutions to visualise the data collected from the field on the web dashboard dedicated to the control room.

4.2. ERMES chatbot functionalities definition & implementation

The ERMES Chatbot design, as previously stated, has specified two versions for two distinct user roles: professional users and citizens. Considering the differences in training and the varying contributions they can make during emergencies, each role is granted access to customised functionalities. For professionals who possess specialised training and expertise in emergency response, the ERMES Chatbot offers advanced features tailored to their specific needs. These functionalities include sharing real-time location with control room operators, sharing their current activity, reporting the in-field situation providing specific details about measurements, damages, and people, receive instructions from the control room.

The system dedicated to the citizens aims to empower citizens to participate in crowdsourcing efforts, provide valuable information to professionals, and help with situational awareness and response coordination. Citizens may have limited emergency response training, which includes functionalities that allow them to actively contribute during emergencies without being overwhelmed with

too much responsibility. These functionalities focus on enabling citizens to report events and hazard-related data, share real-time information, receive broadcasted messages (geolocalised *Communications*), and access relevant safety guidelines (*Tips*). The available functionalities specific to the user profiles are shown in [Table 2](#).

To ensure secure access to the ERMES Chatbot, every user is required to use valid credentials. Currently, the system redirects the users to a dedicated web page. In the future, we would like to offer some bot functionalities to unauthenticated users. When the ERMES Chatbot is launched, users are prompted to perform a login operation by following a link that directs them to a web page. Users can enter their existing credentials or register using a valid email address on this page. Once the email address is verified, users can successfully log in to the ERMES Chatbot.

Upon the first login, the user is guided through an onboarding procedure, designed as a stepped procedure in which the system asks the user to select their role as either a Professional or a Citizen. This step is essential to provide the users with the proper system version. The welcome message for citizens is shown in [Fig. 2](#).

A keyboard displayed in place of the text keyboard behaves like a main menu, suggesting the main topics/actions the user can select. Each command initiates a specific navigation flow, customised depending on the user's role. Topics dedicated to the citizens include *Tips&Quizzes* and *Ranking* ([Fig. 1](#)).

In addition, the application utilises Telegram commands, which are keyword-based inputs preceded by "/", to provide users with quick access to various features and functionalities. For example, the "/start" command allows users to instantly return to the main menu. These commands streamline user interactions and ensure a seamless user experience, enabling efficient navigation and access to specific actions or information within the application.

One of the core activities enabled by the ERMES Chatbot, available both for professionals and citizens, is reporting. A report is a geolocalised set of information that users can create to describe a specific scenario around them. A report can include predefined descriptive parameters enriched by text, audio, photos, or videos. The report creation is a procedure in which the ERMES Chatbot drives the user by asking predefined questions, asking:

- Which hazard or event do they want to report about
- To add a textual description by typing it in the chat
- To add the location (current or selected on the map)
- To add eventual additional media (videos, pictures, audio recordings) by attaching them from the device media or by directly recording them by using the Telegram functionalities

Inputs and system feedback are exchanged as messages and visible on the chat screen. The draft of an empty report template is provided to show which data it can include ([Fig. 3](#)). At this stage, any type of information can be added using Telegram's functionalities. Once all the desired information is added, the report can be either saved as a draft to be completed later on or sent to the control room. After a report is sent, the user can still modify it, for instance, to attach further details. Finally, sent reports can be visualised at any time.

The design and development of the reporting procedure have undergone thorough testing and evaluation, as it is one of the bot's paramount features but also one of the most complex. Recognising the initial complexity that citizens might encounter, an extensive assessment was carried out to refine the process. This involved introducing beside the initially designed procedure ([Fig. 3](#)) a more user-friendly and straightforward approach ([Fig. 4](#)). Users now have the option to initiate the reporting process by simply sending a text message, a voice note, a video, or an image. These two approaches ensure a seamless user experience both for users who prefer a more guided procedure and a direct route to create a report.

Table 2
ERMES Chatbot functionalities for user profiles.

	ERMES Chatbot functionalities for Citizens	ERMES Chatbot functionalities for Professionals
Common features	See Communications See and send Reports Review other users' Reports Adjust Settings	
Specific features	Gamification functionalities	Set the Operational Status and Activity Manage Missions

Fig. 1. – Customised keyboard of topics (main menu of the ERMES Chatbot version for citizens).

Fig. 2. – ERMES Chatbot welcome message.

Fig. 3. ERMES Chatbot screenshots of the main phases in the Report creation and finalisation process.

Fig. 4. – ERMES Chatbot screenshots of the main phases in the Direct Report creation procedure.

The ERMES Chatbot allows users to receive Communications drawn up directly by the control room through a web-based dashboard. Communications are messages that have validity time (start and end time). They can be broadcasted or sent to specified user groups or individuals. Once a Communication is sent, the target people receive a message in the chat. Users can access all the Communications in the dedicated section, accessible from the main menu (Fig. 5).

Moreover, in order to enhance user engagement and promote active participation, we have incorporated gamification elements into the application. With the integration of mechanics (points, badges and levels) and content (feedback messages, quests), users are motivated to actively contribute to the application's functionalities and objectives. Gamified events are specified actions such as reading *Tips*, answering *Quizzes* and submitting *Reports*. Moreover, badges and levels are assigned when reaching specific objectives. Microlearning content is available in the *Tips&Quizzes* section, which citizens can enter from the main menu. *Tips* are short information providing guidance and recommended behaviours organised by hazards and context (Fig. 6a). *Quizzes* are questions about the *Tips* the user can use to assess their awareness or learning level and identify areas where further knowledge or awareness gaps exist (Fig. 6b). Both types of content are categorised based on the different types of hazards, and *Quizzes* are sorted by difficulty level.

The user's progress on the path from citizen to safer citizen is displayed in the *Ranking* section, providing the relative position in the overall ranking, the total amount of points gained per specific action, levels and badges won.

Finally, the system includes a group of *Settings* (Fig. 7) enabling the user to change the language selecting among the five languages currently supported (English, Italian, French, Greek and Spanish). The user can also modify the displayed username and the

Fig. 5. Communications list and details.

Fig. 6. – ERMES Chatbot Tip (a) and Quiz (b) examples.

time zone and apply spatial and temporal filters and location-sharing preferences. From the same menu, the user can also *Logout* from the system.

4.3. Citizens' engagement through gamification

Engaging citizens on sensitive topics such as hazards and disaster prevention is challenging. Several factors concur with it: first of all, the emotional toll that hazards and risk scenarios solicitate, that is related to loss-based emotions, such as fear, regret, worries and anxiety. Although some are universal across cultures, sociocultural factors as well as the causes of the hazards, affect the emotional response of individuals [63]. Even not considered a disease, the literature identifies the construct of eco-anxiety as a family of ecological emotions associated with a particular type of stress and worry related to the environmental crisis ([64,65]). Despite the emotional and cultural barriers, raising attention and promoting awareness and a positive attitude towards disaster risks is paramount.

Gamification consists of the use of game elements in non-game contexts [66]. Other authors ([67–69]) focus on the purpose of changing or stimulating specific behaviour of targets of interest. Over the years, it has been extensively investigated and applied in a wide range of sectors, in the fields of health ([70]), tourism, education [71], public services [72]. Recently, gamification has attracted the attention of governments and administrations interested in experimenting with new ways to interact with the citizens and encour-

Fig. 7. Settings menu.

aging participation through ICT ([73,74]). In the field of DRR, gamification is investigated and experimented as an approach to introduce, inform and engage citizens on environmental monitoring and protection, and respectful behaviours ([26,75]). Gamification mechanisms aim to encourage citizens to produce micro-actions that result in a crowdsourced enhancement of societal welfare without distributing costly incentives, such as reducing energy and water waste, using public transportation, giving feedback to rate services, etc. The gamification design starts with defining goals and the strategy to enrich the experience, with game elements working as triggers and reinforcements to stimulate behavioural changes [67]. Points, badges and leaderboards, the so-called PBL, are considered the essential building blocks of a gamified experience ([76]). These elements are broadly applied, and their effectiveness is investigated [77,78]. The PBL guarantees the possibility of adding a gamified layer of services in an easy and understandable way for providers, developers, and users. Nevertheless, it has been shown to be ineffective or even decrease motivation and performance [79]. Over the years, the basic gamification components have been mapped and specified in terms of psychological mechanisms as well as technical features [80]. The emotional design, narratives and personalisation are among the crucial aspects to be offered to raise and maintain users' interest and provide a sense of meaning and immersion [81].

The mobile applications sector has made heavy use of gamification, and the examples available today are countless. Gamification in conversational interfaces is a more recent topic, investigated as a novel approach to engaging users. Conversational UI may enrich the gamification for training and skill acquisition purposes, thanks to the natural and contextualised dialogue [82] available in the ecosystem of applications and services daily used. Considering the DRR context, a service providing hazard or disaster-related information gamification may introduce additional stimuli, not helpful, distracting or even harmful. On the other hand, risk communication may benefit from gamification to raise awareness and provide beneficial information to handle uncertainty and emotions. Curated content and interesting interactions, added to a positive narrative, can help organisations to inform citizens about risks and behaviours [83].

Based on this background, gamification has been seen as an opportunity to enrich some of the core activities enabled by the ERMES Chatbot. The gamification strategy underlies goals that must be coherent with the main scope of the system, i.e., to raise citizens' awareness and engage them to become reporters, or in other words, active environmental observers able to send relevant and accurate information to the emergency management professionals. The activities to be gamified must be coherent and not interfere with the primary activities and functions. For this reason, micro-learning, reporting and peer reviews have been identified as the activities more suitable to be promoted by applying some basic gamification mechanisms. Communication and reports reading are retrieving information activities that are more likely to be related to hazards or ongoing events, situations and topics in which gamification might be felt as dissonant (Fig. 8).

The ERMES Chatbot gamification entails a path through which the person starts learning about hazards and behaviours (micro-learning), progressively grows as a reporter and, growing in expertise, keeps reviewing the others' citizens' reports, collaborating to a broader environmental protection action. This path is announced during the onboarding, where the value proposition is shortly described (Fig. 9). A dedicated tutorial explains the core elements of the ERMES Chatbot gamification: the path, the points assigned for different actions, badges and levels that result from the reward combinations. A leaderboard shows users their relative position in the user community.

Despite its well-known limitations, the ERMES Chatbot integrates the PBL approach to keep user interaction simple and focus on the main topics of the service. The following figure shows the main desired activities associated with specific mechanics and conversational content.

The ERMES Chatbot score system has been redesigned in different iterations to get to a simpler version: initial medals acknowledging learning progress in specific hazards and DRR phases have been reduced. The system assigns points every time one action of

Fig. 8. – ERMES Chatbot gamification key concepts, including goals, action and Mechanics, Dynamics and Aesthetics (MDA).

ACTIVITIES	ONBOARDING	+ LEARNING	++ MASTERING	+++ REPORTING	++++ REVIEWING
DESIRED BEHAVIOURS	Learn how to grow as a SAFER citizen	Read Tips	Reply to Quizzes	Create Reports Receive Reviews	Review Reports
MICRO CONTENT	Tutorial, Action-oriented commands	Tips	Quizzes	Reports	Reports, Reviews
MECHANICS	Feedback Points	Feedback, Points	Feedback, Points, Badges, Levels	Feedback, Points, Badges, Levels	Feedback, Points, Badges, Levels

Fig. 9. – The ERMES Chatbot gamification desired behaviours and mechanics mapped to the key activities.

the path is performed by the user (Fig. 10). The points gained by reading tips, replying to the quizzes, creating new reports and mastering the specific actions and topics allow the user to collect incremental badges for the specific actions. The incremental combination of points and badges allow the user to proceed on the level system. Each step represents increasing expertise in environmental knowledge and safe behaviours and rewards the active role in reporting. Contextual messages and visual elements provide positive feedback and encourage the person to actively keep on growing on the proposed path, information that is always updated in the leaderboard.

4.4. System architecture and implementation

After carefully considering several options, we developed the ERMES Chatbot using the Telegram platform for three reasons. First, the end-users do not need to install a custom application on their mobile phone but use an existing app that may be already in use. Second, the richness of the provided features and the availability of well-documented web-based APIs. Third, Telegram is available for many mobile Operating Systems: there is an official client app for iOS⁴, Android⁵, wear OS, and desktop and web-based clients. Telegram has 700 million monthly active users and is the second most popular messaging application after WhatsApp. This large user base makes adoption easier.

From a technical viewpoint, Telegram offers a diverse set of pre-built features that significantly enhance the ERMES Chatbot usability. One important functionality is the capacity to easily share the current or live location, which is crucial in scenarios where real-time geographical information is needed, such as during emergencies. Furthermore, Telegram's integration with the device's camera allows for seamless multimedia data sharing, providing users with a quick way to transmit photos or videos directly from the ERMES Chatbot interface. Telegram also allows quick access to media stored on the user's device, facilitating the file-sharing process.

A feature of Telegram that stands out is its commitment to privacy. The platform ensures that bots have limited access to user data, reflecting a conscientious approach to handling personal information. When creating an account on Telegram, users are only required to use a phone number, which, however, remains entirely invisible to other users and bots. These choices in handling personal information help build trust in this platform, showing that Telegram is dedicated to keeping users' information private. Moreover, Telegram offers different structured interactions, such as inline and keyboard buttons, which allow the creation of dynamic and interactive elements directly within the chat flow, enhancing the overall user experience. Telegram's support for commands also allows for more intuitive and direct interactions, enabling users to trigger specific actions or retrieve information with a simple command prompt. Moreover, it allows a seamless integration of support for multiple languages to ensure broader usage. We integrated into the ERMES Chatbot seven different languages: English, French, Spanish, Italian, Greek, Finnish, and Turkish.

While Telegram offers various advantages, it is essential to consider certain drawbacks associated with its use as a platform for bot development. One concern is the dependency on a third-party platform. Developing a bot on Telegram requires compliance with its

⁴ <https://github.com/TelegramMessenger/Telegram-iOS>.

⁵ <https://github.com/TelegramOrg/Telegram-Android>.

Fig. 10. – The ERMES Chatbot PBL (points, badges, levels) system.

policies, features, and updates, and any changes in these aspects could potentially impact the bot's functionality. This compliance introduces an element of uncertainty and necessitates ongoing adjustments to align with the evolving landscape of the Telegram platform. However, the same concern applies even more strongly to ad-hoc applications that must deal with Operating Systems, user interfaces, and framework library updates over a variety of multiple mobile devices. In the following, we provide details regarding the ERMES Chatbot architecture, implementation, and deployment, discussing scalability issues. The technology stack of Chatbot Module, which is the main logical engine of the ERMES Chatbot, is based on *Nest.js*⁶ and *Telegraf.js*.⁷ The latter is a popular, plugin-based JavaScript library implementing a high-level interface for Telegram APIs. The Chatbot Module uses *MongoDB*⁸, a non-relational database, to handle the data persistence required to store users' conversation state while consuming the Telegram API.

As shown in Fig. 11, the Chatbot Module components are.

- The Bot logic, which provides inline menus and custom keyboards for all the functionalities available for users.
- The User Session cache, which stores users' sessions using MongoDB.
- The Client API, which is a web-server that handles all HTTP requests to/from the Bot Logic

The described Chatbot Module is connected to two additional modules: the Crowdsourcing Intelligent Gateway (CIG) and an Authentication Module. The CIG is composed of a Backend API and a relational database (i.e. PostgreSQL), and it serves as a central component responsible for storing and managing the data generated by the ERMES Chatbot, including reports, missions, user information, communications, and notifications. It also facilitates the connection between the Chatbot Module and the web application for control centres aimed to visualise ERMES Chatbot data and manage the ERMES Chatbot users. The CIG ensures seamless data management and secure communication between the Chatbot Module and the web application, enabling efficient retrieval and data presentation.

Both the Chatbot Module and the CIG are connected to the Authentication Module. This module handles the unified login and registration process for users, ensuring secure access to the system. It manages user credentials, including roles and permissions to enforce proper authentication and authorisation throughout the system. The Authentication Module plays a crucial role in maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of user accounts and their associated data.

The overall architecture can be seen as a standalone solution that can be integrated into existing systems by utilising the APIs exposed by the Backend API. This modular design allows for smooth integration with preexisting systems, enabling the ERMES Chatbot functionalities to be easily incorporated into different environments.

Scalability shall be guaranteed to handle traffic spikes that could be generated during big emergency events. To this end, specific frameworks such as Kubernetes can be used to implement a scalable Docker-based application [84], instantiating multiple nodes (i.e., virtual machines) in near real-time according to the application requirements. Alternatively, autoscaling services [85] can be used in case of Platform as a Service (PaaS) systems. The scalability performance assessment of the proposed application is outside the scope of this paper. However, readers interested in further details may refer to Ref. [86,87] where an extensive study has been performed regarding the performances of a crowdsourcing application deployed using the PaaS approach.

5. Validation through user tests

In about 18 months, a total of 53 organisations, 121 practitioners and 159 citizens in four countries (France, Italy, Spain and Greece) have provided feedback on the ERMES Chatbot. In this section, we focus on user tests conducted with citizens sampled from the demonstration attendees to thoroughly assess every function of the ERMES Chatbot in terms of UX.

⁶ <https://nestjs.com/>.

⁷ <https://telegraf.js.org/>.

⁸ <https://www.mongodb.com/>.

Fig. 11. – ERMEs Chatbot architecture.

The sampling criteria to recruit citizens as testers included age (distributed in three age ranges: 18–40, 40–64, over 65) and sex (balanced), plus the mandatory requirement of excluding citizens trained and experienced as Civil Protection volunteers. The involved sample consisted of 18 citizens in four countries (France, Greece, Italy, Spain) balanced per sex (9 women, 9 men), including citizens aged from 22 to 76 (Mean age 44.1), with a medium-high level of education (7 master-degree/Phd; 9 high schools; 2 compulsory education), 100 % Android users but the 72 % never used Telegram. Five people knew the application, and only one person used it regularly. The participants tested the ERMEs Chatbot voluntarily and free of charge.

Six tasks were defined to try and test the main functionalities enabled by the prototype, each of them related to a realistic situation (inspired by the storyline). Initially, the users were asked to follow the onboarding procedure after the sign-in and given the ERMEs Chatbot's purpose and instructions. A short tutorial introduced the users to conversational interaction through prompts and commands. The tasks concerned the report creation and reading, the communication reading, the tips & quizzes exploration, and the leaderboard consultation and settings. The sequence of tasks was predefined but left flexible to let users decide the task sequence. This flexibility allowed us to explore the interest raised by the different ERMEs Chatbot features, guaranteeing that all the users performed all predefined tasks. During the test, the user interaction recording (screen and voice), the thinking-aloud protocol ([88]), a questionnaire including ad-hoc questions and the System Usability Scale (SUS) ([89]) combined with direct observation and contextual interviews, allowed the collection of behavioural and subjective data on the usage and overall experience of the ERMEs Chatbot ([90]). User experience metrics recorded were the duration of each task (in terms of time, the conversation turns), the completion of each task, the number and types of errors that occurred, and the number of help requests to the system and the researchers [91].

The user tests were performed in a dedicated room in individual sessions conducted by one UX expert and assisted by one developer. This configuration enabled the direct observation of the same interaction from different perspectives (human factors and technology), and the agreement on solutions to mitigate them. The data collected during the user tests with citizens are shared on the Zenodo platform and can be accessed via the following URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/10592302>. Fig. 12 provides an overview of the evaluations of the ERMEs Chatbot's single features, assessed in terms of findability (the extent to which the user interface controls are easy to find and retrieve), readability (the extent to which the displayed data and information are easily read), and usefulness (the extent to which the functionality would be helpful in the users' everyday activities).

Two main contents managed by the ERMEs Chatbot were considered crucial, relevant and useful: the Reports and the Communications. The early versions of the reporting function, designed following the requirements of the Civil protections to enable professionals to create reports during their missions, resulted in being too complicated for citizens due to the many choices available, e.g., environmental parameters that citizens cannot know and handle. As a result, the report creation procedure was redesigned to be more “conversational”, leveraging questions and answers, and exploiting the dialogic clues of Telegram. The ERMEs Chatbot for citizens

Fig. 12. Overall evaluation of the ERMEs Chatbot functionalities.

gives more relevance to the input of text, photos and videos as the main content of the in-field reports. This solution has definitively improved the bot's general interaction and perceived usefulness.

After reading the **Reports** created by other users and the Communications sent by the control room, citizens suggested complementing the list of items with a map-based visualisation. Both contents heavily depend on the user's location. In the first case, it is asked to geolocalise the report, and in the second, to receive the alerts for specific areas of interest. Nevertheless, location is very sensitive information and location sharing in Telegram resulted extremely difficult for the users. For these reasons, the location sharing was redesigned to make it clearer and contextual. When creating a report, the user will be asked to provide a location concerning the event they are reporting about by replying to the ERMES Chatbot questions or tapping on a map. Conversation makes this step more natural and transparent. Concerning Communications, the solution enables the citizens to set an area of interest to filter information and communications better to consult via ERMES Chatbot. These design solutions aim to lighten user interaction and make the system more useful, customisable and compliant with the citizens' real needs.

Experts and citizens provided relevant hints on **gamification** applied to DRR and the basic implementations prototyped. Proposing microcontent such as tips and quizzes to test and discover more about the core topics of DRR was considered a valuable approach. It addresses the need for people to learn more about hazards and safer behaviours. Microcontent helps to cope with this topic easily, but they would need a content strategy ensuring to provide content adapted to the user level and frequently updated. In addition, the gamified approach shall be more engaging and proactively recall the users on topics and challenges. Nearly all participants consider the points and rewards assignment for the activities performed useless. This type of service can count on a deep motivation of persons to collaborate, preserve and monitor the environment and community safety. The scoring system and the leaderboard are irrelevant to these values.

In general, the **human-machine dialogue** results well structured: every exchange has a clear start and end, with an acceptable duration/number of turns. The data about the navigation errors suggested how to exploit further the conversational approach, with more straightforward questions and input modalities that people commonly use when chatting, including voice messages, videos and photos. This user requirement encounters the Civil Protection expectations of increasing the media exchange (especially photos and videos) received via crowdsourcing.

The **graphic user interface** integrates the Telegram standard component and ad hoc menus and commands. User tests showed that native Telegram components (keyboard, attachment command, menu for selecting location and media) are difficult to spot, even though they are very similar to other messaging apps. Users do not recognise them as actionable elements and tend to neglect them. This limitation is offset by ad-hoc commands, providing the available options for the context. These elements help the users to understand how to interact quickly, use the different functions and keep the orientation when moving from menus and content.

The System Usability Scale (SUS) is submitted at the end of every user test to get an overall evaluation of the system confirms the appreciation of the sample. The average SUS is 64,31 out 100 (Min = 45; Max = 87,5). [Fig. 13](#) shows the average score per single item of the SUS.

The activities conducted have produced relevant suggestions on the usability and utility of the ERMES Chatbot and its purpose was very appreciated. Citizens acknowledged and appreciated the possibility of having a channel for crowdsourcing data according to the Civil Protection requirements. In general, it resulted very clear that this service does not overlap nor substitute the official channels of communication, especially during an emergency and that it aims to foster safety and collaboration between people and responders. The decision to implement the ERMES Chatbot through an existing messaging app is also valuable and innovative, even though the involved segment of the population does not largely adopt Telegram. The iterative design review and the user tests are precious sources of information to learn about the impact of some design solutions on future usage in the real context. The feedback elaboration, insights and recommendations were then incorporated into a wireframe and visual mock-up to be discussed and refined with the stakeholders and developers.

The most impactful future improvements envisage the introduction of a shorter procedure (sketched in [Fig. 4](#)). This solution intends to increase the naturalness of the conversational interaction, allowing the system to receive spontaneous input from the user di-

Fig. 13. – System Usability Scale scores.

rectly typing the text field of the chat, as in the familiar chatting sequence. The system will accept different types of input (text, photos, video, audio messages) to start a conversation, driving the report creation through simple questions. The procedure shall significantly reduce complexity and steps. Additional non-functional clues, such as tone of voice and feedback regulation, will strengthen the conversation. The Gamified approach requires a redesign. Enhancing the micro-content is essential for motivating users to engage actively. Tips and Quizzes shall be implemented to be more relevant, interesting, and tailored to specific target users. Solutions to encourage the continued engagement of the users are envisaged in a more proactive system behaviour, with periodic information updates and quests to call the citizens to know and gradually enter the collaborative loop of environmental monitoring.

6. Limitations and future works

The proposed ERMES Chatbot offers numerous valuable features and benefits, however it still presents some limitations that need to be addressed in future developments. Using an external messaging service, i.e., Telegram, has both advantages and drawbacks. While this choice provides the benefit of leveraging a familiar and widely used messaging service, drastically reducing the maintenance effort of the application, it may limit the level of customisation compared to developing a custom app from scratch. However, by optimising our ERMES Chatbot's features within the constraints of the Telegram messaging service and leveraging a user-centred design process, we can enhance its adaptability and tailor it even more effectively to the specific needs of DRR. Moreover, we intend to enhance the usability of this tool by incorporating users' feedback and harnessing the observations gathered through a testing phase with citizens. By actively listening to user perspectives and addressing their needs, we aim to continuously enhance the overall user experience, ensuring that it remains intuitive, efficient, and effective in supporting users in their tasks and objectives.

One of the challenges we encountered is the reliance on internet connectivity and potential network congestion, which can affect the ERMES Chatbot's responsiveness in disaster situations or areas with limited connectivity. Unfortunately, given the dependence on the Telegram platform, if there is no connectivity, the ERMES Chatbot cannot be used. Similarly, if the ERMES Chatbot produces a workload that the architecture cannot sustain, or a downtime occurs, the platform will register a temporary failure. Another aspect to be further addressed is the cultural barrier that we observed in all countries toward the adoption of new existing services, such as Telegram, which is very similar to other messaging applications widely used.

Despite the platform's robust privacy measures designed to safeguard user data, the platform still encounters resistance due to personal habits and preferences. A way to overcome this limitation could be by developing an ad-hoc application. However, this approach poses its own set of obstacles, as introducing a stand-alone app would face challenges in terms of market competition, users' reluctance to download new applications and relinquishing the advantages derived from relying on a third-party platform. The extensive user base, credibility, and familiarity associated with established platforms like Telegram would be abandoned, making the adoption of a custom app a complex and potentially less viable alternative. Nowadays, DRR relies on relevant innovations based on mobile technologies and apps dedicated to crowdsourcing for environmental monitoring.

Nevertheless, the galaxy of mobile applications employed by organisations like local authorities, civil protection and associations, causes the fragmentation of services, and by consequence of the usage, limiting the data and information exchanged. Providing a service through an existing platform is a strategy to reach a wider audience by exploiting an existing user base and to ensure better user experience, customisation, and better security and privacy protection. Instant messaging apps allow the spread of information and updates in real-time to many people based on their location.

A future challenge is to introduce and integrate innovative digital services into DRR practices and operational protocols, because setting and enabling crowdsourced data collection from the territory in an useful way for emergency management practitioners is still an open issue. An important aspects that could be tackled using recent multimodal foundation models, is related to the validation mechanisms of crowdsourced data, which shall prevent the sharing of inaccurate or false information.

7. Conclusions

This study presents the ERMES Chatbot, a conversational tool developed to support DRR processes. It is designed to improve communication, collaboration, and information exchange among DRR stakeholders, including citizens. By providing a direct channel for citizens to engage with local responders, the ERMES Chatbot transforms them into active participants in an integrated DRR process. The conversational interface has been tested and proven to facilitate interactive dialogues, enhance communication, and foster collaboration throughout all phases of disaster management.

The ERMES Chatbot is effective in offering real-time collection and storage of structured information such as data, images, and videos, which are often difficult to capture with traditional systems. It also incorporates geolocation features for better emergency management coordination, and supports multiple languages, broadening its accessibility.

Moreover, the ERMES Chatbot offers valuable functionalities across all phases of the Disaster Risk Management cycle. It includes insightful knowledge pills on self-protection behaviours, while providing a two-way communication channel for reporting hazards and receiving updates.

Finally, the involvement of domain experts and end users throughout the design and development process resulted in the effectiveness of the proposed conversational approach. With a well-developed content strategy, the ERMES Chatbot can effectively supports enhanced coordination and citizens engagement, improving the effectiveness of the overall DRR process.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Angelica Urbanelli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Antonella Frisiello:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Luca Bruno:** Supervision, Software. **Claudio Rossi:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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